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EDUCATION, SOCIETY AND PSYCHOANALYSIS: POSSIBILITIES FOR A RELATIONSHIP CRITIQUE

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ABSTRACT: The objective of this search is to search _ relationship between psychoanalysis and education, possible elements what exceed The psychologization From problems educational essentially in origin Social, policy and economic. However, one cannot rule out the aspect fruitful of this relationship, which can be the use of hermeneutics psychoanalytic allied to criticism culture dialectic. To us we appropriate a reading frankfurtiana of Freud 's thought , we seek Show The importance of psychoanalysis for reflection on the production of knowledge, on the teacher - student relationship and for the denunciation of attitudes pedagogical merely adaptive and no emancipatory. if The ambiguity of cultural formation, and, in sense strict, education, no can be eliminated simply with a scale - receipt terminological, It is assignment gives Theory critique oppose you concepts to reality. Therefore, cultural formation is the denial of what we experience up until then: semiformation socialized (Halbbildung) possible in to be seized at education per through parameters _ pedagogical that not has in-depth your reflection about The culture and The theory of knowledge, about The democratization of teaching The cultural industry and the Law Suit unconscious existing at relationship school - society. We claim the effort theoretical in contraposition to practicality reigning in the interventions made in for the sake of education.

Keywords: Education. Psychoanalysis. Critical Theory. Society.

INTRODUCTION

In face gives concord totalitarian what touts immediately as sense The elimination of the difference , it is possible that temporarily , until even something of the social force of liberation behold withdrawn to the individual sphere , and in Brazil , psychoanalysis he was welcome us speeches pedagogical as form in solve O problem in “ children maladjusted ”, “ abnormalized fur quite Social”. So , in relationship at children labels of up until then of “ abnormal ”, defending , in the field of mental hygiene , the insertion of theory psychoanalytic . Abstaining from the analysis of institutions , task attributed to sociology , mental hygiene aimed diagnose , prevent and correct personality and conduct problems , the cause of which would be at influence power of misfit means , conflicts households , malnutrition , labor exploitation , drugs . _ For Arthur Ramos, no there would be only the “ child problem “, but substantially “ child problems “ socially determined not to demanded - laugh one criticism of society as a whole , rather a “ correction ” of the family environment by through adult analysis . __ Although Arthur Ramos detect the cause of maladjustment , essentially , as action of the environment , in a perspective eugenics , had as assignment fundamental “ transform you impulses that go against the environment in impulses Useful to middle .

DEVELOPMENT

Despite the advance in the ideas pedagogical Brazilians , to the criticize theories _ racists and geneticists who predominated at explanation of failure school, he was maintained The tradition in “ no if speak gives force in the house of the hanged man ”, or that is , never attributing “ maladjustment “ to the division of class society . However , it is possible think one contributed psychoanalysis to education in moldsno conservatives?The psychoanalytic knowledge can something do to individual who, having explicit your unconscious , you have to return to a partnership __ regulated by the objectification of the conscious ? Obviously psychoanalysis lends itself to the critique of knowledge and society , but not stop being her same social product .

individual and society they can dispose of psychoanalysis as instrument of clarification , but the desire not to know can be relegated to second plan .

No they are us horizons of this job to recover one likely education psychological , whose attempts , disconnected from a society criticism , _ has been so little profitable at the sense in improve The health mental _ From individuals , much any less suggest one transposition , without more , gives clinic “.. for some little room encrusted in the corner hidden from a school ” which would be , at the very least , obscurantism .

THE school by _ your ambivalence , deserved from Adorno a certain look and listen psychoanalytic in order to clarify in it the tension between culture and barbarism . To space circumscribed to the school , it is suggested to formation and conscience psychoanalytic tools for teachers , parents and students . However , this clarification no aims properly ends pedagogical , but anti -pedagogical . Assuming the procedure common to Critical Theory , the negation determined that understands knowledge _ as complaint of illusion , it is deposited in the school the few possibilities to do in front of barbarism civilized . if at school effort is allied to psychoanalysis – _ per example , the inherent taboos to the teachers being thought and resolved at own formation professional in instead of being your base , not would you like say we have found the solution unique and definitive however , “...a clarification a little enough and just partially efficient it ‘s still better than none ”

This illustration via listening psychoanalytic and self- reflection criticism - in a word , thought – and experience , from which the de - barbarization be possible , have in their favor the action anti- pedagogical aspect of psychoanalysis that does not he must go to meeting of improvement , but of the disarticulation of the school as we know it , experience it and perpetuate it . the doctrines pedagogical are essentially egoic , to the seek control and predictability of development _ child ‘s cognitive and emotional _ _ to take in account The impossibility structural of that domain . an education analytics

only would be possible at the moment in which the education resign to your own foundation . It is therefore necessary to make a differentiation between education and discourse about education , pedagogy . The knowledge of the impossibility of controlling the unconscious doesn't just lead to a position ethic extremely valuable . take us to power think one education no totalitarian and emancipatory .

O rigor with what you dominators prevented at the course From centuries to your own descendants , well like the masses dominated , relapse in ways of life mimetics – starting with the prohibition of images in the religion , passing through the social proscription of actors and gypsies and finally arriving at a pedagogy that wean children from being _ children - is the very condition gives civilization . THE education Social and individual reinforces us men your behavior objectively While workers and prevents them from getting lost in the fluctuations of nature environment . All fun , all abandonment it has something of mimicry . It was by stiffening against it that the ego was forged . It is through in your constitution that the passage takes place gives mimesis reflector for reflection controlled .

What is fundamental is not the reappropriation of the mimetic as magic and regression : mimesis would indicate much most one dimension essential of thinking , That dimension in approximation no violent , playful _ One approach of other what get understand it without arrest him and oppress him, knowledge without violence nor domination . That knowledge only would be possible with the recognition of strange , as defined Freud: O secretly familiar that was subject The repression , but returned , anyway , O what it should to have remained hidden but came to light.

That weird would be everything it says respect for nature no totally conformed fur process civilization , which refers to mimesis original , dispossessing the subject of himself same , as the corporeality , the experience aesthetics , O suffering . O welcome and conviction with you conflicts and joys of otherness no they are us limits of a therapy , since this other one is socially

located in the “ misfits ”, “ abnormal ”, “ weak ” who do not match with you taxes in productivity , efficiency and obedience . if “ everything that did n't fit fully or that hurts you prohibited in which secular progress has settled has an effect irritating and provokes one repug - nancy compulsive ” the ethics of compassion require not only self - knowledge via enlightenment psychoanalytic , but a transformation Social: production mode bourgeois , the indelible heritage mimetic of all praxis is abandoned to oblivion . You men obsessed with civilization only if realize in their own strokes mimetics , what if became taboo in certain gestures and behaviors that find in others and that stand out in your world rationalized as waste isolates and traces rudimentary truly shameful _

Therefore , the criticism at production relations and knowledge _ so due allow overcome theories _ explanations of failure , of maladjustment , which seek level and empty the contradictions of the process civilization , locating them in the biological and/ or silencing the determinations social .if the construction civilizing it is founded at denial of the unconscious , of the capacity mimicry , so that one can claim you powers of conscience , reason , exploitation of work , the greatest contribution that psychoanalysis __he can to give to education is, precisely , to show its impossibility . It is necessary leave you exaggerations aside to seek a balance point _ _ in which the educator can benefit from psychoanalytic knowledge . In psychoanalysis nothing is true but your _ exaggerations . At this point , maybe be need Search for not the point of equilibrium , but the point of disequilibrium , where the conflict space _ can be explained and what was _ mute -do can be heard . A pedagogy that takes the phenomenon of consciousness seriously _ contradictory no would be interventionist , dirigiste , totalitarian , would rather work for the resistance . But this amounts to pedagogy think your _ historicity , to look into yes same , to make possible The education emancipatory .

Suppose a teacher having worked on Freud 's ideas and in Marx if decide for the criticism of humanism bourgeois _

THE leave of that moment , the education would be a problem for him and not one solution , because what there is to form another one when the strength is known irreducibility of the unconscious and the dissimulation systematic of exploitation through the morality of responsibility ? For such a teacher, form no would be inform to the students about of those questions and discuss them with they ? But as could that teacher has the intention of training for “ freedom ” knowing the role corrosive and repressive of culture as superego and the meaning of a society that reproduces itself by replacing repression (of body and spirit) through exploitation economic ? No would this teacher be playing precisely us limits and in illusions of humanism ?

It is hypothesis only can be lifted , let's see well , in a perspective in which you glimpse no only psychoanalysis , but the thought of Marx. This data is essential in this situation hypothetical cited per Chauí . IT IS one certain reading Marxist in Freud what he can become fruitful The relationship between psychoanalysis and education . In the following Adorno's considerations , we observe a positioning critical before the “ limits and illusions of humanism ” , from a reading of Freud and Marx:...the knowledge psychological defended as theory precisely by Freud (...) is found in agreement also with the possibility of sublimating in such a way the called aggression instincts , about which even he _ _ manifested conceptions quite many different during your life , so precisely _ they lead to trends productive . Therefore , I believe that in fight against barbarism or in your elimination there is a moment of revolt that could he own be designated as barbaric , if we started from a concept formal of humanity . But since everyone _ we us we find in the context of own guilt _ system , nobody will be entirely free from traces of barbarism , and all will depend on guiding Those strokes against principle of barbarism , in instead of allowing your course in towards the disgrace .

The watchword is , therefore , the defense condition immediate from survival of humanity , historically threatened , not a concept ahistorical of humanity . Psychoanalysis is not enough for that ,

because the structure dynamics of the psyche presented by Freud – the relationships between O Id, Ego and Superego – already no are enough in capitalism monopolist :

psychoanalysis _ introduced the little internal company that was thus constituted _ as one dynamics complicated of the unconscious and the conscious, of the id , ego and superego. In the conflict with the superego , the control instance _ Social at the individual , O ego keeps at pulses inside From Limits gives self -preservation ... But in the era of the great corporations and wars world , the mediation of the social process by countless monads appears retrograde . _ You subjects of the economy instinctual are expropriated psychologically and this economy It is managed most rationally for the own society . THE decision what O individual he must to take in each situation no need most result from a painful internal dialectic of moral conscience , self -preservation and drives . for the people at ball professional , decisions are taken by the hierarchy that goes from the associations up until The management national ; at ball private , fur scheme gives culture in mass , what expropriates their consumers forced from their last impulses internal . Associations and celebrities _ assume at functions of ego and of Super ego, and at pasta , stripped down up until even the appearance of the personality , they allow themselves to be modeled much most docilely , according you models and words in order given, of what you instincts for the internal censorship . If, in liberalism , the individuation of a part of the population was condition of adaptation of society _ _ in your all to stage of the technique , today , the operation of the apparatus economic require one direction of the masses who do not be disturbed by individuation ... The irrationality of adaptation docile and applied to reality becomes , for the individual , more rational than the reason .

Thus , the “ work of culture ”, object of psychoanalysis , expresses at sentence “ where there was the Id, let there be the Ego”, does not consubstantiate due to siege of subjectivity and the encapsulation almost unconscious automatic . _ so much so that already it 's not possible speak without “ sublimation ” caveats From instincts ” for

the which The civilization it would have if engendered up until so but from your domestication to increase productivity and consumption . _ the creativity and The fruition for the art they are reduced The release and to immediate training of the unconscious via technicism and cultural industry . the result of this no it can be culture why has per principle and purpose The indifferntiation . You individuals of beings social conform , then , to the category of beings socialized what is your own denial . we live in one situation in which for many – in understanding since it’s already a shame say “I”. Hence the need for a criticism that thinks about the “ thingification of souls”: “ Technology is the owner of no only yours _ bodies , but also of their spirits ...”. The task of psychoanalysis , in this sense , would be to denounce the socialization progressive , result gives weakening of ego in the current conditions of material survival that perpetuate the barbarism : like today in day is extremely limited possibility to change the assumption objectives , that is, the social and political ones that generate such events , the attempts to oppose repetition of Auschwitz are impelled necessarily to the side subjective .

No there may be cultural criticism without critique of relationships in work and production , because culture is constituted at materiality and on historicity . But reflect about Is it over there presupposes a to look what surpass O unveiling of the class struggle that it would be hiding . Without that horizon We do only what Adorno calls “ cultural criticism ” summoned and closely hitched The a concept uncritical gives culture , in what O critical cultural think to have concluded your task , to to do The correspondence in between O object The to be criticized and you interests in classes what he reflects , The criticism immanent continue looking for real content _ implicit at falsehood. THE psychoanalysis, in this sense , It is a time privileged dacritic immanent , then Freud analyzed with seriousness O contents in truth of formations psychic . Adorno explains well what he understands by criticism immanent / dialectic of culture , in general lines , to consider that it is posture before the object is that of not hypostasis you standards

cultural nor that of if restrict The terms operational , The The end in to do justice The she , O what no means a involvement complete at the object and, yea, transcend gives conscience , as categories of understanding , beyond immanence . _ “only it will be able to follow the dynamics object ‘s own who in him no you are completely developed ”. That double movement in direction to object (involvement and not involvement) is a subsidiary of Freud ‘s critique of culture , of consider that it is done for and against the interests of the individual . Also important to consider _ _ _ The impossible - of we be completely and totally oblivious to mechanisms ideological . the educator needs to be a critic of culture , more than a citizen sincerely concerned about citizenship . critique immanent and dialectic of culture and self- reflection criticism are assumption fruitful of a relationship between psychoanalysis and education that has as point of departure and arrival to transformation of conditions objective . Psychoanalysis , therefore , is not incompatible with _ _ education , but with the doctrines pedagogical , to the enable at least one redirect _ _ at formation of teacher.

If the findings Freudians , such as the unconscious and hermeneutics psychoanalytic , no match the promises of the culture , they can be critical references of knowledge and education , through which this knowledge has been legitimized . THE school , emerging as answer to birth of the state, of the family , of property deprivation and the social division of labor , the malaise at education is a result of malaise at civilization . To withdraw from confrontation as horror is to allow it to perpetuate itself . the ignorance in the face of suffering provoked by the mechanisms of domination is it own . In others words : ... education need take seriously what already _ deha much is known to philosophy : queo fear no he must to be repressed . When O fear no It is repressed , When us allow - mos to have really so scared how much this reality demands , then precisely per That via will disappear probably great part From effects deleterious of fear unconscious and repressed .

It is no wonder that the educational process you have failed. To mute, hide, or simply not know your taboos and your side obscure, the school community – and, in last instance, civilization sees herself imprisoned per This one hidden which is manifested by example, in what he calls “double hierarchy”, observable at school, in which pedagogical research it should pay special attention: “...the hierarchy official, according to intellect, performance, grades, and hierarchy unofficial, in which the force physics, “being a man” and a whole set of skills practical physical no honored by the hierarchy official play a paper”.

“To be man” put yourself in opposition to effort intellectual. In this duo hierarchy, in which the division between labor is expressed physical and work intellectual, there also the problem of competition – grades, selected classes (the well-known “A” classes), whose strengthening is contrary The one education human. In that case, there is one apparent appreciation from work intellectual because, after all, if the important thing is to be the strongest – no matter if physics or mentally – the cultural formation is already abolished why undifferentiated with your otherwise, to the analyze those who have answer to everything, consider that: “the intelligent people have always made things easier for barbarians, because are stupid”. If the school intends humanize the individual, it is necessary to focus on the inhuman in the human.

It is necessary assume the wound narcissistic provoked by the discovery of the unconscious, recognizing that barbarism implied at culture no he must be at the service of a teacher weakening. Knowledge is not imposed, but it is not he can dismiss The authority. The human being autonomous and therefore emancipated – no constitutes simply protest against any type in authority, to which you see O time gives authority as assumption of emancipation. But glorification and conservation of this time constitutive of individuality leads to the sense contrary to desirable, or that is, to minority in the sense Kantian: the inability to make use of one’s own understanding. People become – emancipated The leave

gives identification with authority, with later frustration with it and its overcoming. However, it occurs quite often The identification with the aggressor.

The adaptation process, which takes place in a painful way, passes, necessarily, by an exaggerated realism in relation to you even. Adorno understands that the criticism This one realism overvalued, the stuff of identification with the aggressor, needs to be evaluated, above all, in the first childhood.

To analyze The ambivalence gives relationship teacher – student and society – teacher is wanted rare to understand The aversion to teaching that is not limited to only at considerations about being a poorly paid profession. There is in this aversion Law Suit unconscious that already no are based on facts goals, but give account of motivations subjective little discussed and by that same worrisome. Being a teacher implies to charge The scribe image of monk – disempowered – storms, from someone holder of little knowledge – efficient in a world where, implicitly, the force physical determines considerable part of life Social.

This implies that, despite the abolition of punishments physicists at school and the so propa-sides children’s rights, there are The Image teacher’s unconscious as torturer, jailer, executioner, of one who has power about beings fragile per your range age or per your ignorance. Towards The scarcity structural of our schools, the teacher does not it achieves go much in addition to a keeper children. Of any way, inequality inherent in the relationship pedagogical put the teacher in situation suspicion and eternal vigilance, making him, at the same time, same time, an eternal watched in your reactions, in your preferences affective – which, incidentally, is not he must express, under penalty of being considered unfair. From a castrator, the teacher becomes a neutered:

On the one hand, he no has occupation erotica; on the other hand, it plays a big role paper erotic for teenagers dazzled by example. But in most cases – only as object

unattainable ; just observe in him traces of sympathy , to defame him as unfair .

This exclusion almost always just formal of the sphere erotic , concealed most of the time in sublimation – the teacher has to be an example of discretion and self -control as herald of civilization , is reflected at conscience mutilated that not tolerates the free expression of the body . The disposition of the portfolios , the “keep quiet ” order are more than postures disciplinary - is the immobilization physical expressing the enclosure of the spirit . THE indifference with The own pain and The pain of other It is The brand of this education for the discipline through O rigor, Image veil of sadism and of masochism , so expensive to fascism. the relationships objects at school deserved one special attention from Adorno. Precisely per no be discussed , become taboos , prohibiting the distinction between work and _ purpose and affection staff . A fully-fledged teacher goal , or be professional _ strictly , would appear inhuman and cold , but give flow rate yours effectiveness without being able to have control about that is to submit to representations that are made his . Being that the teachers no should repress their affections for later leave them sprout rationalized , without recognize them _ towards yes and the too much :

Probably a teacher what says : “yea, I am unfair , I l’m one person as you , to whom something pleases and something displeases ” will be most convincing than another supported ideologically - logically at justice , but that ends inevitably _ _ committing injustices repressed .

This us refers to the issue of school evaluation and the implications that the behavior student ‘s disciplinary has about she . How can the teacher effectively evaluate the student more _ humane and just , if it is not possible for he gives himself account of the contradictions inherent he own ? It seems to us that it is not just ethics _ professional , but to put yourself at the table of discussions pedagogical as much as subjective has a teacher - student relationship and not simply put the teacher in neutral position to evaluate _ some thing . In the case of failure , one is at the mercy , and

this is the expression of the democratization of education - of vehement appeals verbal and formal (features in instances superior to the school), enough for them to be valid only any mistake or forgetfulness of the teacher or the collective of teachers in the evaluation process . Although you speeches no be so explicit , the teacher is effectively not considered able to assess your _ work and its impact on students . Uncertainty , weakness , falsehood and injustice are concepts that involve teaching , without this _ _ can be said clearly and recognized .

THE requirement of objectivity for the teacher who must contain , repress everything that is subjective at your relationship with the students also it is related to the maintenance of society that fears the different and the potential transformer contained in the particular. an understanding criticism of what if intends with it is objectivity and O what there is in so fearsome at subjectivity the teacher-student relationship perhaps could bring to the ours horizons some humanization perspective . _ the subject he can save in if a power objective still greater than categorizations comprehensive and pre-established – the so - called criteria of scientificity in positivism or the concept of style in the arts , by example . in the world totally managed , the process persecutory against _ objectivity of the subject (understood as subjectivity in a sense of immorality and incompetence to discern) is used to leave you in eternal impotence . Thus , objectivity , which has per The end unmask postures ideological , yes, she same instrument _ ideological to treat everyone _ as things .

CONCLUSION

Addressing subjectivity critically allows analyze and transform the conditions objective no only of the individual , but of the society that the besiege . At explanations psychological are partial , but necessary , The measure that can unmask the forces irrational , which, in name of reason , dominate coercively the individual .

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The school he comes suffering consequences through the modifications in function of your action transformer to over the years. Today therefore insert all your _ acting in the context critical to meet the evolution of modernity and play a role no conservative most dynamic , follow O time transformer globalized so the psychoanalysis it is

contained and expands the action of speaking and listening in the sense most broad to unmask the forces irrational , which, in name of reason , dominate coercively the individual .

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